

ISic3018

I.Sicily inscription 3018

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Buscemi

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50158

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332327

1. [— — — — — — — — — —]
2. [Π]αίδε [σσι(?) καὶ Ἴαννα]
3. καὶ Ἄπ [όλλωνι(?) — — —]
4. παρεγέ [νοντο(?) — — —]
5. μετὰ Π [— — — — — — — —]
6. [θυ(?)]γατ [— — — — — —]
7. [— —] καὶ [— — — — — —]
8. [— —] τῆ τριακά [δι — — —]
9. [— — ε]ύχαρι [στοῦντες(?)]
10. [Παίδε]σσι [καὶ Ἄπόλλ]-
11. ωνι καὶ Ἴαννα.
- 12.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645366

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Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 464

Manganaro, G. 1992. Iscrizioni "rupestri" di Sicilia. In Gasperini, L.(eds.), *Rupes loquentes: atti del convegno internazionale di studio sulle iscrizioni rupestri di età romana in Italia. Roma - Bomarzo 13-15.X.1989*. Rome. pp. 447-501. At 459 no.4

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